

Notes

Dioxomolybdenum Complexes of N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines

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In recent years, a large number of stable and well defined dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of the type, MoO_2L_2 (LH = bidentate ligand) have been isolated and characterised.¹⁻⁶ N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines (Ar. N(OH) : C(Ph) : N. Ar') have been introduced very recently as a new class of analytical reagents for carrying out gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of transition metal ions⁷⁻¹¹. In the present investigation is reported the preparation and characterisation of the 1:2 complexes, formed by hydroxyamidines with dioxomolybdenum(VI).

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus : N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diaryl benzamidines were synthesised according to the method reported earlier^{1,2}. All the complexes have been prepared under similar experimental conditions. A typical preparation is described here.

An aqueous solution of 0.30g of molybdenum 0.003 M) as $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.552 g) was diluted to 50 ml and warmed to 60°. To this, was added dropwise with constant stirring ethanolic solution

of N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2, 6 dimethyl) phenylbenzamidine hydrochloride (2.33 g, 0.006 M). The solution was diluted to 150 ml and the orange-yellow complex was digested over a boiling water bath for 30 min and filtered. It was washed with hot water followed by a small volume of 10% ethanol. Crystallisation of the complex from absolute ethanol gave orange-yellow shining needles. The complex was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried at 105° and finally in vacuum over fused CaCl_2 .

The compounds were analysed for molybdenum by igniting a known amount of the dried complex to MoO_3 and also by digesting the complex with a mixture of nitric, sulphuric and perchloric acids and subsequent gravimetric determination employing oxine^{1,3}. Nitrogen content of the complexes was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method. The molybdenum complexes are soluble in dioxane, methanol, ethanol and higher alcohols. They are stable towards heat, light and air and can be stored for a long time without any deterioration.

Room temperature magnetic measurements were made by a Gouy balance using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as a calibrant. The conductance values of the methanolic solutions of the complexes were measured at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with Systronic conductivity bridge [model 302]. Infrared spectra of the solid complexes were studied as mulls in hexachlorobutadiene and nujol and recorded on Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer equipped with sodium chloride optics. The electronic spectra of all the complexes were recorded with Carl Zeiss 'Specord' using 1 cm matched quartz cuvettes. The relevant physical data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR DIOXOMOLYBDENUM COMPLEXES OF N-HYDROXY-N, N'-DIARYIBENZAMIDINES

No.	Ar	Ar'	Mol. Formula	Colour	M.P. °C	% Analyses	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	MoO ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ OCl) ₂	yellow	212	N, Mo,	7.19 12.42 7.26 12.44
2.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	MoO ₂ (C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ OCl ₂) ₂	yellow	215	N, Mo,	6.54 11.38 6.67 11.42
3.	C ₆ H ₅	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	MoO ₂ (C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O) ₂	orange-yellow	216	N, Mo,	7.50 12.63 7.39 12.65
4.	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	MoO ₂ (C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O) ₂	Deep yellow	153	N, Mo,	7.31 12.12 7.21 12.20
5.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	MoO ₂ (C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ OCL ₂) ₂	orange-yellow	205	N, Mo,	6.70 11.57 6.77 11.59
6.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	MoO ₂ (C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ OCl) ₂	orange-yellow	190	N, Mo,	6.80 11.62 6.77 11.59
7.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	MoO ₂ (C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ OCl) ₂	orange-yellow	198	N, Mo,	6.65 11.56 6.77 11.59

For the preparation of the complexes No. 1 and 2, corresponding hydroxyamidine free bases, and for 3-7, hydroxyamidine hydrochlorides have been used.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) suggest the general formula of the complexes to be MoO_2L_2 . The conductance values of the molybdenum complexes in methanol ($10^{-3}M$) are around 5 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$. This indicates the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements show them to be diamagnetic as expected for $4d^0$ system. The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in ethanol comprise of three bands having λ_{max} around 213 nm, 253 nm and 316 nm. The nature of the absorption curves of the dioxomolybdenum complexes is practically identical to the absorption curves of the corresponding free ligands with only slight variations in the position and intensity of the band maxima. Moreover, the complexes do not show any absorption band in 360-700 nm region. All these characteristics agree well with the observations made in other dioxomolybdenum complexes¹⁻⁶.

IR spectral data of these Mo(VI) complexes have been of use to infer the bonding of the ligand in the complex. The band at 3085 cm^{-1} attributed to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding¹⁴ in the hydroxyamidine free bases disappears from the spectra of the corresponding molybdenum complexes. The sharp band at $935 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable as N-O stretching band^{15,16} in all the free ligands is displaced to higher frequency with an increase in intensity on complexation. These facts indicate deprotonation of the hydroxyl hydrogen and formation of a M-O bond.

The $\text{C}=\text{N}/\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching band^{17,18} in the ligands assigned in the region $1595\text{-}1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shifted to the lower frequency side in the complexes. The position and intensity of this band is of the same order in all complexes, irrespective of their preparation from hydroxyamidine free bases or hydrochlorides. Thus, it is very likely that the deprotonation of the $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{H}$ hydrogen of the hydroxyamidine hydrochloride takes place during complex formation. This is also supported by the fact that the broad band centered at $2525\text{-}2750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, originated most probably from the stretching vibration of $=\text{N}-\text{H}$ group¹⁹ in hydrochlorides³⁻⁷ (Table 1) is absent in their corresponding dioxomolybdenum complexes. All these facts favour the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom and the formation of a $\text{C}=\text{N}\dots\text{M}$ bond.

The presence of dioxomolybdenum species, $\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$, in the chelates is established from the infrared spectra of the complexes. Since, both ν_1 and ν_3 of cis MoO_2 group are i.r. active, two very strong $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ stretching bands are observed²⁰⁻²¹. The absorption band around 880 cm^{-1} arises most likely from MoO_2 asymmetric stretching and that around 918 cm^{-1} represents symmetric MoO_2 stretching vibration. The existence of a true dioxomolybdenum species ($\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$) is indicated by the lower value of the symmetric stretching frequency, as oxometal cation involving a single oxygen-metal multiple covalent bond has been described to absorb at a considerably higher region around $970\text{-}980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{22,23}

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